

Matrix Forms of Fractional Euler's Formula and Fractional DeMoivre's Formula

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Abstract: In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we obtain the matrix forms of fractional Euler's formula and fractional DeMoivre's formula. In fact, our results are generalizations of classical calculus results.

Keywords: New multiplication, fractional analytic functions, matrix forms, fractional Euler's formula, fractional DeMoivre's formula.

I. INTRODUCTION

In 1695, the concept of fractional derivative first appeared in a famous letter between L'Hospital and Leibniz. Many great mathematicians have further developed this field. We can mention Euler, Lagrange, Laplace, Fourier, Abel, Liouville, Riemann, Hardy, Littlewood, and Weyl. Fractional calculus has important applications in various fields such as physics, mechanics, electrical engineering, biology, economics, viscoelasticity, control theory, and so on [1-11].

However, different from the traditional calculus, the rule of fractional derivative is not unique, many scholars have given the definitions of fractional derivatives. The common definition is Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional derivatives. Other useful definitions include Caputo fractional derivatives, Grunwald-Letnikov (G-L) fractional derivatives, and Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivatives to avoid non-zero fractional derivative of constant function [12-16].

In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we obtain the matrix forms of fractional Euler's formula and fractional DeMoivre's formula. In fact, our results are generalizations of classical calculus results.

II. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1 ([17]): If x, x_0 , and a_n are real numbers for all n , $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as an α -fractional power series, that is, $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}$ on some open interval containing x_0 , then we say that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is α -fractional analytic at x_0 . In addition, if $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is continuous on closed interval $[a, b]$ and it is α -fractional analytic at every point in open interval (a, b) , then f_α is called an α -fractional analytic function on $[a, b]$.

In the following, we introduce a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions.

Definition 2.2 ([18]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Assume that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional power series at $x = x_0$,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}, \quad (1)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}. \quad (2)$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} g_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} \otimes_{\alpha} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) (x-x_0)^{n\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} & f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) \otimes_{\alpha} g_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} n} \otimes_{\alpha} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} n} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} n}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Definition 2.3 ([19]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})$, $g_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})$ be two α -fractional analytic functions defined on an interval containing x_0 ,

$$f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} n}, \quad (5)$$

$$g_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} n}. \quad (6)$$

The compositions of $f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})$ and $g_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})$ are defined by

$$(f_{\alpha} \circ g_{\alpha})(x^{\alpha}) = f_{\alpha}(g_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} (g_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}))^{\otimes_{\alpha} n}, \quad (7)$$

and

$$(g_{\alpha} \circ f_{\alpha})(x^{\alpha}) = g_{\alpha}(f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{n!} (f_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}))^{\otimes_{\alpha} n}. \quad (8)$$

Definition 2.4 ([20]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x is a real number. The α -fractional exponential function is defined by

$$E_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} n}. \quad (9)$$

On the other hand, the α -fractional cosine and sine function are defined as follows:

$$\cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{2n\alpha}}{\Gamma(2n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2n}, \quad (10)$$

and

$$\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n x^{(2n+1)\alpha}}{\Gamma((2n+1)\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (2n+1)}. \quad (11)$$

In addition, the α -fractional hyperbolic cosine and hyperbolic sine function are defined as follows:

$$\cosh_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \frac{1}{2} [E_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) + E_{\alpha}(-x^{\alpha})] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n\alpha}}{\Gamma(2n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} 2n}, \quad (12)$$

and

$$\sinh_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) = \frac{1}{2} [E_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) - E_{\alpha}(-x^{\alpha})] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{(2n+1)\alpha}}{\Gamma((2n+1)\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (2n+1)}, \quad (13)$$

Proposition 2.5 (fractional Euler's formula): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, then

$$E_{\alpha}(ix^{\alpha}) = \cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) + i \sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}). \quad (14)$$

Proposition 2.6 (fractional DeMoivre's formula): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and k be a positive integer, then

$$[\cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) + i\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} k} = \cos_{\alpha}(kx^{\alpha}) + i\sin_{\alpha}(kx^{\alpha}). \quad (15)$$

Definition 2.7: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and A is a matrix. The matrix α -fractional exponential function is defined by

$$E_{\alpha}(Ax^{\alpha}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A^n \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(A \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^{\alpha} \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} n}. \quad (16)$$

III. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we provide the matrix forms of fractional Euler's formula and fractional DeMoivre's formula.

Theorem 3.1 (matrix form of fractional Euler's formula): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, E is the unit matrix and I, J are matrices such that $I^2 = -E, J^2 = E$. Then

$$E_{\alpha}(Ix^{\alpha}) = E\cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) + I\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}), \quad (17)$$

and

$$E_{\alpha}(Jx^{\alpha}) = E\cosh_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) + J\sinh_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}), \quad (18)$$

Proof

$$\begin{aligned} & E_{\alpha}(Ix^{\alpha}) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} I^n \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \\ &= E + I \frac{x^{\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + I^2 \frac{x^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} + I^3 \frac{x^{3\alpha}}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} + I^4 \frac{x^{4\alpha}}{\Gamma(4\alpha+1)} + \dots \\ &= E + I \frac{x^{\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} - E \frac{x^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} - I \frac{x^{3\alpha}}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} + E \frac{x^{4\alpha}}{\Gamma(4\alpha+1)} - \dots \\ &= E \left[1 - \frac{x^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} + \frac{x^{4\alpha}}{\Gamma(4\alpha+1)} - \dots \right] + I \left[\frac{x^{\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} - \frac{x^{3\alpha}}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} + \dots \right] \\ &= E\cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) + I\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand,

$$\begin{aligned} & E_{\alpha}(Jx^{\alpha}) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} J^n \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \\ &= E + J \frac{x^{\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + J^2 \frac{x^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} + J^3 \frac{x^{3\alpha}}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} + J^4 \frac{x^{4\alpha}}{\Gamma(4\alpha+1)} + \dots \\ &= E + J \frac{x^{\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + E \frac{x^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} + J \frac{x^{3\alpha}}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} + E \frac{x^{4\alpha}}{\Gamma(4\alpha+1)} + \dots \\ &= E \left[1 + \frac{x^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} + \frac{x^{4\alpha}}{\Gamma(4\alpha+1)} + \dots \right] + J \left[\frac{x^{\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \frac{x^{3\alpha}}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} + \dots \right] \\ &= E\cosh_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) + J\sinh_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}). \quad \text{q.e.d.} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.2 (matrix form of DeMoivre's formula): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, n is an integer, E is the unit matrix and I, J are matrices such that $I^2 = -E, J^2 = E$. Then

$$[E\cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) + I\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} n} = E\cos_{\alpha}(nx^{\alpha}) + I\sin_{\alpha}(nx^{\alpha}), \quad (19)$$

and

$$[E\cosh_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) + J\sinh_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} n} = E\cosh_{\alpha}(nx^{\alpha}) + J\sinh_{\alpha}(nx^{\alpha}). \quad (20)$$

Proof By matrix form of fractional Euler's formula,

$$[E\cos_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) + I\sin_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} n}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= [E_{\alpha}(Ix^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} n} \\
 &= E_{\alpha}(Inx^{\alpha}) \\
 &= E\cos_{\alpha}(nx^{\alpha}) + I\sin_{\alpha}(nx^{\alpha}) .
 \end{aligned}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned}
 &[E\cosh_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha}) + J\sinh_{\alpha}(x^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} n} \\
 &= [E_{\alpha}(Jx^{\alpha})]^{\otimes_{\alpha} n} \\
 &= E_{\alpha}(Jnx^{\alpha}) \\
 &= E\cosh_{\alpha}(nx^{\alpha}) + J\sinh_{\alpha}(nx^{\alpha}) .
 \end{aligned}$$

q.e.d.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we obtain the matrix forms of fractional Euler's formula and fractional DeMoivre's formula. In addition, our results are generalizations of ordinary calculus results. In the future, we will continue to use the new multiplication of fractional analytic functions to solve the problems in fractional differential equations and applied mathematics.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. C. Koeller, Applications of fractional calculus to the theory of viscoelasticity, Journal of Applied Mechanics, vol. 51, no. 2, 299, 1984.
- [2] B. M. Vinagre and YangQuan Chen, Fractional calculus applications in automatic control and robotics, 41st IEEE Conference on decision and control Tutorial Workshop #2, Las Vegas, Desember 2002.
- [3] R. Hilfer, Ed., Applications of Fractional Calculus in Physics, World Scientific Publishing, Singapore, 2000.
- [4] M. Teodor, Atanacković, Stevan Pilipović, Bogoljub Stanković, Dušan Zorica, Fractional Calculus with Applications in Mechanics: Vibrations and Diffusion Processes, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2014.
- [5] F. Duarte and J. A. T. Machado, Chaotic phenomena and fractional-order dynamics in the trajectory control of redundant manipulators, Nonlinear Dynamics, vol. 29, no. 1-4, pp. 315-342, 2002.
- [6] Mohd. Farman Ali, Manoj Sharma, Renu Jain, An application of fractional calculus in electrical engineering, Advanced Engineering Technology and Application, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 41-45, 2016.
- [7] V. E. Tarasov, Mathematical economics: application of fractional calculus, Mathematics, vol. 8, no. 5, 660, 2020.
- [8] R. L. Magin, Fractional calculus models of complex dynamics in biological tissues, Computers & Mathematics with Applications, vol. 59, no. 5, pp. 1586-1593, 2010.
- [9] R. Caponetto, G. Dongola, L. Fortuna, I. Petras, Fractional order systems: modeling and control applications, Singapore: World Scientific, 2010.
- [10] R. Almeida, N. R. Bastos, and M. T. T. Monteiro, Modeling some real phenomena by fractional differential equations, Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences, vol. 39, no. 16, pp. 4846-4855, 2016.
- [11] V. V. Uchaikin, Fractional derivatives for physicists and engineers, vol. 1, Background and Theory, vol. 2, Application. Springer, 2013.
- [12] K. Diethelm, The Analysis of Fractional Differential Equations, Springer-Verlag, 2010.
- [13] K. B. Oldham and J. Spanier, The Fractional Calculus, Academic Press, Inc., 1974.
- [14] S. Das, Functional Fractional Calculus, 2nd ed. Springer-Verlag, 2011.
- [15] I. Podlubny, Fractional Differential Equations, Academic Press, San Diego, Calif, USA, 1999.

- [16] K. S. Miller, B. Ross, An Introduction to the Fractional Calculus and Fractional Differential Equations, John Wiley & Sons, New York, USA, 1993.
- [17] C. -H. Yu, Research on fractional exponential function and logarithmic function, International Journal of Novel Research in Interdisciplinary Studies, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 7-12, 2022.
- [18] C. -H. Yu, Fractional differential problem of some fractional trigonometric functions, International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Innovations, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 48-53, 2022.
- [19] C. -H. Yu, Research on two types of fractional integrals, International Journal of Electrical and Electronics Research, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 33-37, 2022.
- [20] C. -H. Yu, A study on fractional derivative of fractional power exponential function, American Journal of Engineering Research, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 100-103, 2022.